

Finlaggan - 1450

Lost medieval home of the Lords of the Isles

Image: Interior of the main hall from the Finlaggan reconstruction (Credit: Open Virtual Worlds).

In the late medieval period, Loch Finlaggan in Islay of the Inner Hebrides was an important power base. The two islands of Eilean Mor (or Large Isle) and Eilean na Comhairle (or Council Isle) on the loch were the site of a major residence of the Lords of the Isles, who governed the Hebrides and parts of mainland Scotland and Ulster. A complex of buildings spanned the two islands, connected by a causeway, and served as the administrative and ceremonial centre. Research has revealed the comfort and wealth of the area, with dogs wearing decorative collars, and the Lords and their followers enjoying music, imported wine and board games. The lordship was traditionally held by the MacDonald family, who rule stretched from Antrim in Ireland to the north east of Scotland.

Drawing on the findings of the Finlaggan Archaeological Project, researchers at the University of St Andrews and Smart History have created a new digital reconstruction of Finlaggan as it may have appeared in the fifteenth century – in the latter phase of its medieval glory days. During this period, the Scottish kings were trying to reign in the influence of the MacDonalds. In the 1490s, for instance, James IV sent a military expedition to sack Finlaggan, destroying many of the buildings. The site subsequently sank into obscurity.

How Did We Know What to Reconstruct?

Since the early 1990s, the Finlaggan Archaeological Project (led by Dr David Caldwell), in collaboration with the National Museum of Scotland and the Finlaggan Trust, has been uncovering evidence of this site's residential, administrative, and ceremonial significance. The archaeological work has been paired with documentary and material object research and comparison to other late-medieval sites.

How Was the Reconstruction Created?

A digital landscape was created using survey data and height map. Models were created in 3D modelling programs and imported into UNREAL (a cross-platform game engine for creating virtual worlds). The models were then scaled, orientated and assembled. The landscapes were populated with flora and fauna. Where applicable, models of characters and animals were imported and animated.

How Has the Reconstruction Been Used?

It is part of the wider [CINE](#) project which focuses on digitally representing heritage in northern environments.

When Was the Reconstruction Published?

This version of the reconstruction was released to the public in 2018.

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How to Access the Reconstruction?

There is a video preview of the reconstruction on [Vimeo](#).
A 360° tour can be found on [Roundme](#).

You can walk through the reconstruction as part of the VR exhibit at the [Finlaggan Visitor Centre](#).

The app, [Lords of the Isles: 15th Century Finlaggan](#), guides you through the reconstruction

A tour of the reconstruction by David Caldwell as part of the Heritage at Home series can be found [here](#). Additional tours of the reconstruction can be viewed [here](#).

Discover More

Information held by Historic Environment Scotland about Finlaggan can be accessed via [Canmore](#). CANMORE

You can see how Loch Finlaggan looks today on [Google Maps](#).

The full history of the site, including Finlaggan Castle, can be read at [Wikipedia](#). W

More information about the project can be found on the [Open Virtual Worlds website](#).

Media

BBC: [Lords of the Isles medieval home in Islay recreated](#)

Scotsman: [Inside the medieval home of the Lords of the Isles](#)

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